

Thermodynamics and Stability Constants of Uranium-Aspartic Acid Complex

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Uranium (VI) complexes of aspartic acid as a ligand have been studied potentiometrically in aqueous media. Presence of one complex has been established. The stability constant of the complex formed were computed at three different temperatures. Log K_1 values were found to be 8.34, 8.93 and 10.40 at 30°, 40° and 50° respectively. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS calculated at 30° are -11.53 K.cal./mole, -25.966 K.cal./mole and -47.67 cal./deg./mole respectively.

The review of the literature shows that a few complexes of aspartic acid are studied¹. But no reference could, however, be traced out in the literature on the study of uranium compounds of aspartic acid. Although few workers have calculated stability constants of uranyl complexes with different ligands like β -methyl tropolones³, 8-Hydroxy Quinoline-7-Sulphonic Acids⁴. Tsai-Teh Lai and Song-Jey Wey⁵ studied polarographically uranyl complexes in dextro and levo aspartic acids.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of aspartic acid in the absence and presence of UO_2^{2+} against 1N NaOH.

Curve A.—20 ml 0.04M Aspartic Acid + 1 ml 1M HClO_4 .

Curve B, C and D.—20 ml 0.04M Aspartic Acid + 10 ml 0.04M UO_2^{2+} + 1 ml 1M HClO_4 .

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

Aspartic acid was a gift from Hexagon Laboratories, U.S.A. Its solution was kept in refrigerator. The titration vessel consisted of a tall form Pyrex beaker provided with a plastic lid through which the electrodes and the jet of the semi-micro burette were introduced and the solution was stirred magnetically before recording every reading. The whole assembly was suspended in thermostat, where the temperature was controlled electrically up to the variation of 0.1°.

The experimental procedure involved a series of pH titrations of ASPA with standard NaOH in the absence and presence of UO_2^{2+} at various ligand to metal ratios at three different temperatures, 30°, 40° and 50°. All the pH-titrations were performed in aqueous 0.1 M NaClO_4 solution.

R E S U L T S A N D D I S C U S S I O N S

The stoichiometry of the reaction between UO_2^{2+} and ASPA was determined by potentiometric titrations of mixtures of reactants in various ratios against standard alkali.

The pH value of the systems B, C, and D is lower than the corresponding pH value in system A (Figure 1) indicating the liberation of proton due to the complex formation

In all the three cases a colour change was observed at about $\text{pH} = 3.5-4.0$ from light yellow to intense yellow colour. The precipitate was seen after pH 4.4, 4.6 and 3.9 in the curve B, C and D respectively; the reaction may be

It clearly indicates that the complex is stable only up to pH 4, after which hydrolysis starts and at pH 4.4 uranyl hydroxide precipitates.

A peculiar phenomenon has been observed in curves C and D. The proton liberated in both the cases corresponds to the reaction

The horizontal distance between the two sets of curves (A C and A D) indicates that perhaps the zwitter ion releases the proton, explaining more consumption of sodium hydroxide.

The metal ligand ratio in the complex happened to be 1 : 2. The formation curves for these titration sets also indicate increasing value of $\bar{n}$.

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Formation curves for the metal ligand systems (Figure 2) were drawn between the $\bar{n}$, and $-\log[\text{Asp}]$ where the values of these terms were obtained by a method explained by Yatsimirskii⁸.

Fig. 2. Formation Curve of UO_2^{2+} .

The values of $\log k_1$ was read directly from the graph at $\bar{n}$ values of 0.5 and was found to be 8.34, 8.93 and 10.40 at 30°, 40° and 50° respectively and were tallied with values obtained by calculations. The differences were ± 0.15 , 0.12 and 0.1 at 30°, 40° and 50° respectively.

At higher temperature where the possibility of 1 : 2 complex is presumed, the $\log k_2$ was calculated as 8.8 at 50°.

Thermodynamic Functions : The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) of complex formation have been determined⁸ at 30°, and found to be ΔG , ΔH and ΔS as -11.53 K.cals/mole., -25.966 K.cals/mole, -47.67 cal/deg/mole respectively.

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